

Investigating the therapeutic potential of a Poly Herbal Formulation (PHF) in the treatment of Acute Lung Injury murine model

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A preliminary survey conducted across Assam involving traditional healers landed us with various Mono/Polyherbal formulations (MHF/PHF) prescribed for the treatment of different diseases like jaundice, sepsis, dermatitis, asthma, pneumonia and chronic disorders and the formulation for lung disease was selected for authentic scientific validation using murine model. The formulation was prepared by mixing together the different plant parts in a specific proportion and the methanolic extract was prepared and chosen for performing anti-oxidant (DPPH radical scavenging, NO scavenging, Phosphomolybdate assay) and anti-microbial tests (*E. coli*, *Candida albicans*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). The methanolic extract was further subjected to LPS (1 mg/kg) induced ALI murine model study (12 hr, 24 hr and 36 hr) involving biochemical (ALT, AST assay), molecular (AQP expression and ELISA for cytokines) and histopathological parameters. The extract was capable of protecting the mice against the detrimental effects of ALI involving the lowering the ALT and AST levels, reinstating the basal AQP expression level (*aqp1*, *aqp5* and *aqp9*), decreasing the cytokine levels (IL-4 and IL-6) and restoring the normal lung structure altered by LPS. Also, the LC/GC-MS analysis of the extract revealed the presence of pharmacologically potent phytoconstituents (hexadecanoic acid, tetradecanoic acid, quinine, tetrazepam, pygenic acid, asiatic acid, atenolol etc). Thus, the methanolic PHF extract demonstrated anti-ALI effects in LPS induced murine model.

Keywords: Poly-herbal Formulation, Acute Lung Injury, LPS, ELISA, phytoconstituents.